

Is there an intergenerational difference in the perception of tourist guide service quality?

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Abstract

The perceived service quality offered by tourist guides is regarded as a significant determinant in travelers' overall satisfaction with their tour experience. The objective of this study is to ascertain the variations in the opinion of service quality among tourists from different generations with regards to tourist guides. The qualitative research method of interview technique was employed within the parameters of this study. The data for this study were obtained from a sample of 30 participants who engaged in guided tours. These individuals belonged to the X, Y, and Z generations, and their responses were gathered through semi-structured interviews. The study's demographic comprises travelers belonging to Generations X, Y, and Z who have actively engaged in guided tour experiences. The study employed stratified purposive sampling as its sampling technique. The data were subjected to analysis using the MAXQDA 2022 software. Based on the findings of the investigation, it was determined that there exist variations in the perception of tourist guide services across different generations.

Keywords: Tourist Guide, Generations, Service Quality

1. Introduction

Tourists and tourist guides are integral components of the tourism business, contributing significantly to the facilitation and execution of tourism activities. Tourists visiting a popular destination with the intention of immersing themselves in an unfamiliar culture may find it beneficial to have the assistance of a knowledgeable guide who can facilitate the transfer of information. Consequently, tourists exhibit a preference for availing themselves of the expertise provided by tourist guides when visiting unknown areas (Değirmencioğlu & Ahipaşaoğlu, 2003). The provision of services that align with the desires and expectations of tourists visiting a particular area is considered a crucial responsibility of tourist guides, who are entrusted with a range of tasks and obligations (Gündüz, 2002). The tourism industry is a sector that involves a high level of engagement with the concept of service. The occupation of a tourist guide is a specialized area of employment within the tourism sector that mostly involves providing services (Yarcan, 2004). According to Huang, Hsu, and Chan (2010), the provision of high-quality service by tourist guides can yield several positive outcomes in various domains. These include enhancing the country's image,

increasing tourist satisfaction and loyalty, fostering intentions to revisit, mitigating negative perceptions, contributing to the national economy, and serving commercial objectives for the affiliated agency.

The assessment of service quality provided by tourist guides is determined by the examination of their performance in meeting tourists' expectations. Performance evaluations are utilized to ascertain the requirements for service quality of tourist guides. The establishment of criteria aims to enhance the working conditions of tourist guides and facilitate the collection of more impactful feedback. Customer pleasure is achieved by providing visitors with a high-quality service (Parasuraman, 1988). Hence, the level of quality perceived by tourists during a guided tour exhibits a clear correlation with the level of service rendered (Ap & Wong, 2001). The provision of high-quality service by tourist guides has the potential to positively influence tourists' length of stay in a given destination and contribute to their overall satisfaction with the service received. The performance and service delivered by the tourist guide are factors that can be linked to the overall quality of a tour (Geva & Goldman, 1991). The satisfaction of tourists can be achieved through comprehending their demands and delivering services

that align with those demands. Tourists who have their expectations met and are satisfied might provide evidence of the tourist guide's adherence to their professional responsibilities. Despite the existence of numerous studies in the academic literature pertaining to service quality within the tourism industry, such as those conducted by Wang, Hsieh, and Huan (2000), Ap and Wong (2001), and Zhang and Chow (2004), there remains a dearth of research investigating potential disparities in the perception of service quality among different generations specifically in relation to tourist guides. The objective of this study is to ascertain whether there exists a disparity among generations in their assessment of the quality of service rendered by tourist guides.

2. Conceptual Framework

Service Quality

The notion of service is a fundamental aspect that permeates the collective existence of the entire human population (Karatepe, 1997). The orientation towards the concept of service has witnessed an increase in correlation with the development of mankind and the improvement in the welfare levels of societies (Öztürk, 2011). Lovelock and Wright (2007) provide a definition of service as a set of economy-oriented interactions that occur between customers and service marketers. The views of services are subject to alter when persons experience shifts in their living standards. It has been observed that persons who experience an increase in their degree of welfare place significance on the notion of quality prior to the provision of services. Quality is consistently prioritized in service delivery within this particular setting (Toprak, 2007). The notion of quality, a pervasive aspect across several domains, holds significant importance for all sectors (Cowell, 1984). According to Kobu (1999), quality is characterized as the extent to which something is suitable for its intended purpose. The evaluation of firms or persons delivering services and products often involves the use of quality as a criterion (Abdullah & Mohamad, 2016). In essence, scholars refer to quality as the act of evaluating the anticipated level of service against the actual performance rendered (Parasuraman et al., 1985). According to Devebakan and Aksaraylı (2003), the significance of service quality is on par with the concept of quality itself, as it is crucial for the sustainability of enterprises in many sectors. The significance of quality has witnessed a notable escalation over the course of time, primarily attributed to many factors including shifts in customer expectations, rising prices, and a more competitive business landscape. The significance of the quality idea and the imperative of service quality have been recognized by service-intensive sectors, including

service organizations and tourism, as evidenced by the research conducted by Boonitt and Rompho (2012). According to Uygur (2017), service quality is achieved when the service delivered aligns with the consumer's expectations. The concept of service quality is defined as the alignment of product preparation and presentation with consumer expectations, taking into consideration their wants and wishes (Oral, 2001). The significance of service quality is widely recognized across all sectors. Service quality may be described as the assessment and analysis of business performance by consumers (Budiwan & Efendi, 2016). The assessment of the extent to which service providers fulfill client expectations is a crucial determinant in evaluating the alignment between service quality and consumer expectations (Yousapronpaiboon, 2014).

The significance of the concept is underscored by the ability of customers to depart from the firm with a sense of satisfaction, as noted by Oh (1999). Satisfaction can be conceptualized as the evaluative process wherein tourists compare their initial expectations with the actual service received (Oliver, 1981). Measuring service quality is a challenging task due to its multidimensional nature, as noted by Kang (2006). In his seminal work, Grönroos (2000) amalgamated his prior research endeavors and delineated a set of seven distinct criteria. The service quality model encompasses several key dimensions, including professionalism and skills, attitudes and behaviors, accessibility and flexibility, reliability, atmosphere, reputation and environment, and service outcome. In summary, the concept of service quality holds significant importance within the realm of enterprises and the tourist sector, as it can influence several factors including image, satisfaction, loyalty, trust, and repeat destination selection.

The Quality of Tourist Guide Services

Tourism is characterized as an industry that has a high degree of service provision. In the tourism business, the matters of quality and service efficiency hold significant importance within the given environment (Otto & Ritchie, 1996). Tourist guides play a crucial role within the tourism industry, as they have significant duties towards both the sector and the profession. These responsibilities encompass the provision of high-quality service and the creation of satisfactory experiences for tourists (Ap & Wong, 2001). According to Iskhakova (2010), the level of satisfaction experienced by individuals using services is contingent upon the caliber of service rendered by the personnel responsible for service delivery. Consumers perceive the process of assessing services to be more complex in comparison to evaluating products (Liu et al., 2015). Although customers possess the ability to assess the observable attributes of items, such as packaging and

color, it is important to note that these aspects do not factor into the rating of service quality. Hence, it is crucial to consider the behaviors, attitudes, and performances of service providers, along with other environmental elements, when evaluating service quality (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Tourist guides who fulfill the role of intermediaries by escorting guests to their destinations are expected to adhere to a range of criteria. One of the most crucial characteristics is possessing personality features that are universally acceptable from an ethical and moral standpoint. The standards expected of tourist guides encompass a range of attributes, including possessing knowledge, demonstrating strong analytical skills, exhibiting proficiency in language usage, maintaining appropriate posture, employing gestures and facial expressions effectively, displaying a good sense of humor, possessing narrative abilities, and other relevant qualities. The correlation between the guide's provision of services that align with visitor expectations based on these criteria and the generation of tourist satisfaction has been documented in previous studies (Mossberg, 1995; Wang, Hsieh, & Huan, 2000; Wong, 2001; Heung, 2008). The performance of the tourist guide is closely linked to both the quality of service offered and the overall success of the tour (Geva & Goldman, 1991). The significance of tourist guides' service accomplishments, efficacy, and the contentment of tourists has great importance in fostering the growth and advancement of the tourism sector (Zhang & Chow, 2004). Hence, the enhanced speed, heightened reliability, and increased accuracy of the information delivered by the tourist guide directly correspond to the elevated level of service quality exhibited by both the guide and the tour. The potential for issues that may arise during a high-quality trip will be mitigated. Tourist guides play a significant role in shaping visitor satisfaction through the provision of high-quality services in the destinations they visit. The level of satisfaction experienced by tourists can have a beneficial impact on the destination's image and the visitors' opinion of the quality of service provided (Schmidt, 1979; Pearce, 1984; Whipple & Sharon 1988; Mossberg, 1995; Baum, Hearn & Devine, 2007). In their study, Zhang and Chow (2004) identified a set of 12 criteria that can be utilized to assess the service quality aspects of a tourist guide.

- Interpretation (The capacity to interpret) - Emergency (The ability to handle emergency situations) - Polity (Exhibiting politeness towards guests)

- Friendliness: The establishment should prioritize creating a welcoming and amicable environment. - Neatness: It is important for the establishment to maintain cleanliness and present a visually appealing appearance. - Atmosphere: The establishment should

strive to cultivate a relaxed and friendly atmosphere for its visitors. - Assistance: The staff should be readily available to provide assistance in any given situation. - Financial impact: The establishment should aim to positively influence the purchasing behavior of its visitors. - Caution: It is advisable for the establishment to exercise caution in its operations. - Communication: The staff should possess the ability to communicate effectively in many languages, facilitating easy interaction with visitors. Conscientiousness is characterized by the trait of honesty.

The aforementioned criteria are categorized utilizing three distinct views.

- Interpretation (Ability to interpret)
- Emergency (Ability to cope with emergencies)
- Polity (Being polite to guests)
- Friendliness
- Neat (to look clean and pleasant)
- Atmosphere (Creating a relaxed and friendly atmosphere)
- Help (To be able to help in any situation)
- Money (Influencing the visitor's buying attitude)
- Caution
- Communication (Knowing different languages and being able to communicate easily)
- Conscientiousness
- Honest.

These criteria are classified using 3 perspectives.

- Ability: Communication, Interpretation, Emergency, Polity.
- Costumer: Friendliness, Neat, Atmosphere, Help.
- Firm: Money, Caution, Conscientiousness, Honest.

The tourist guide possesses the characteristic of serving as the primary representative in the provision of services. Hence, it holds a significant role in shaping the level of service quality. By doing an analysis of the service quality aspects pertaining to the tourist guide, it becomes possible to ascertain the specific services that elicit visitor satisfaction, as well as those that fail to meet visitor expectations. Consequently, the aforementioned criteria can also serve as a means to identify areas in which tourist guides may need to enhance their skills and abilities, as they can assess their own performances (Grabowski & Geng, 2000). In the present setting, enhancing the service quality of tourist guides can contribute significantly to various aspects such as national and regional development, destination management, sector growth, agency effectiveness, and particularly the performance of tourist guides.

Generational Differences and Service Quality

The birth of the notion of generation is attributed to the observation that persons born in close proximity to one another, spanning from the past to the present, have similar challenges and respond to the demands of their respective time periods (TDK, 2021). According to Howe and Straus (1991), a generation can be defined as a community of persons who were born in close chronological proximity and share similar socioeconomic conditions. On the other hand, Mannheim (1998) describes a generation as a society comprised of individuals who exhibit common cultural practices and behaviors. McCrindle and Wolfinger (2010) underscore the significance of the biological delineation and highlight the crucial role played by the historical differentiation of periods between parents and their offspring in the establishment of generations. The definitions indicate that there are distinct qualities that vary among generations as a result of periodic differences, which is a shared aspect among generations. Hence, it is plausible that individuals who are born within the same generation may display comparable patterns of behavior (Chen, 2010). The persistence of generational differences results in individuals exhibiting a resistance to adapting the norms and behaviors associated with the generation in which they were born, regardless of the evolving conditions in subsequent years. Furthermore, it has been observed that these behaviors facilitate the distinction between the current generation and previous generations (Kim et al., 2016). The distinct attributes of each generation arise from the shared attitudes, behaviors, and beliefs that individuals within the same generation develop as a result of their exposure to common events throughout a specific time period (Sarıtış & Barutçu, 2016). The classification of generations is mostly based on the concept of age (Şenturan et al., 2016). The utilization of generational classification is widely regarded as a highly effective method throughout several service provider sectors. According to Jin, Line, and Ann (2015), businesses and service providers that cater to individuals by considering generational differences assert that addressing the specific needs of different generations enhances individual satisfaction, encourages greater consumer spending, and fosters a sense of loyalty. Nevertheless, relying just on age as a criterion for market segmentation is inadequate (Fountain & Lamb, 2011). According to Giljeard (2004), researchers place significant emphasis on two crucial factors for assessing generational distinctions. These phenomena refer to the occurrences that are witnessed within a specific timeframe, leading to the development of shared awareness and beliefs among individuals. In the present environment, it can be observed that individuals hold comparable perspectives and beliefs

as a result of significant historical occurrences, namely World War I (1914-1918) and the emergence and widespread adoption of television (1940-1950). These milestone events have had a profound impact on society, as noted by scholars such as Mannheim (1952), Kupperschmidt (2000), Lower (2008), and Joshi, Dencker, and Franz (2011).

Based on the classification proposed by Williams and Page (2011), those born within the time frame of 1965 to 1977 are identified as members of Generation X. Individuals belonging to Generation X commenced their transition into adulthood during a period characterized by challenging economic circumstances and very modest living standards. In contemporary times, the current generation exhibits a shift in priorities, with a decreased emphasis on achievement as a primary objective. Instead, they place significance on fostering strong familial bonds and demonstrating dedication towards their professional endeavors. Furthermore, this generation has a comparatively lesser attachment to traditional values and customs when compared to preceding generations. Communicating with Generation X can provide challenges due to various factors. When consumers make a purchase decision regarding a service, they typically consider their surroundings and are influenced by word-of-mouth marketing. Furthermore, it is worth noting that persons belonging to the current generation exhibit a certain level of skepticism towards services and products, while also displaying a heightened sensitivity towards technology (Lissitsa & Kol, 2016). Individuals who were born between the time period spanning from 1977 to 1994 are commonly categorized as belonging to Generation Y. This age is characterized by the notable advancement of women in society, the widespread integration of technology into individuals' lives, the growth of social and interpersonal relationships, and a strong emphasis on achieving success. While the younger generation of consumers in contemporary society tends to deviate from conventional ways, the adult demographic may exhibit consumption patterns that are rooted in traditional practices. The cohort commonly referred to as Generation Z encompasses individuals who were born between the year 1994 and the present day. The current cohort of individuals is commonly referred to as the traditionalist generation, characterized by a strong affinity for technology and a deep concern for familial relationships. The concept of group affiliation holds significant importance for the present generation. This generation is widely regarded as possessing the highest levels of creativity and self-assurance. According to Williams and Page (2011), individuals place importance on the viewpoints and responses of their peers when making decisions about acquiring a certain service.

In order to ensure their survival within their respective sectors, service companies and other service providers must prioritize the significance of service quality. Achieving success within a highly competitive context and surpassing rival entities can be accomplished through the provision of a superior product and the delivery of high-quality services. In the present scenario, industries that heavily rely on service provision must ensure that their services align with customer expectations. Additionally, it is crucial to identify the factors contributing to variations in individuals' perceptions of service quality. This may be achieved by gaining an understanding of the unique demands of each consumer community (Zameer et al., 2015). Several research in the existing literature have examined the variations in the perception of service quality across different generations (Pendergast, 2009; Jang, Kim & Bonn, 2011; Jin & Lee, 2016). According to the findings of Gürler and Erturgut (2019), there exists variability in the perception of service quality within the aviation business, which can be attributed to intergenerational disparities. The research conducted by Dedeoğlu, Çalışkan, and Boğan (2019) examined the impact of generational differences on consumers' perceptions of physical service areas in the context of hotel businesses. The findings of the study indicated that the interaction among different generations has a distinct influence on how services are perceived. Research on intergenerational disparities in the assessment of service quality is linked to the observation that persons within each generation inhabit distinct cultural and social contexts. Within the given environment, variations may arise in the way persons from different generations see service. According to Sullivan et al. (2009), there is a tendency for persons within the same generation to exhibit comparable attitudes and actions. However, it is important to note that there can still be variations in preferences and circumstances among individuals belonging to different generations. Within this particular context, it becomes imperative to ascertain the intergenerational variances in the assessment of service quality exhibited by employees in the sector, specifically focusing on tourist guides who hold significant relevance within the domain of the tourism business.

3. Methodology

In this current research, it is aimed to determine the intergenerational differences in the perception of the service quality of the tourist guide in guided tours. Within the scope of the study, the interview technique, which is among the qualitative research methods, was utilized. The interview technique allows the researcher to collect more detailed data by examining the researched subject in depth (Tekin, 2006). The population of the study consists of tourists in

Generation X, Y and Z who have participated in a guided tour. Stratified purposive sampling was used in the study. In stratified purposive sampling, a sample is selected from a predetermined stratum in line with the study objective (Johnson & Christensen, 2008). Thus, ten people from each generation (X, Y, Z) who participated in a guided tour were interviewed, totaling 30 people in total. The classification made by Williams & Page (2011) was used for generation classification. Individuals born between 1965 and 1977 are called Generation X, individuals born between 1977 and 1994 are called Generation Y and individuals born between 1994 and the present are called Generation Z.

Before the data collection phase, a literature review was conducted. A semi-structured interview form was preferred as a data collection tool. The interview form consists of seven questions. Research data were collected from tourists who participated in guided tours in April 2023. Each interview lasted an average of 20 minutes and the data were recorded by the researcher. The first part of the interview form consists of demographic information and the second part consists of research questions about the service provided by the tourist guide. The interview form was developed by utilizing the studies of Wong (2001) and Heung (2008) and then the opinions of 10 experts who are academicians and tourist guides in the field of tourist guiding were obtained.

Interview Form Questions

- Your gender
- Your Birth Year (1965-1977) -(1977-1994) - (1994 and present)
- Did the tourist guide have basic professional skills?
- Can you evaluate the tourist guide in terms of communication skills?
- Can you evaluate the tourist guide's relations with the guests?
- Were you satisfied with the service provided by the tourist guide? If you are not satisfied, can you explain the reasons?
- Would you like to join a tour with the same guide again?

Descriptive analysis was used to analyze the research data. The purpose of descriptive analysis is to organize and interpret the data collected as a result of interviews or observations and present them to the reader. A cause and effect relationship is established between the findings obtained depending on the theoretical background (Kvale, 1994). The data obtained through the interview technique were transferred to the computer environment and the MAXQDA22 program was used to perform the analysis. In order to protect

confidentiality in the research, the participants were named as X1, Y1, Z1....

4. Findings

Upon examination of the demographic data, it is evident that the birth years of the individuals involved in the study may be categorized into three distinct generational groups: 1965-1977, 1977-1994, and 1994

to the present. Each generation consists of an equal number of 5 female and 5 male participants. Upon examination of the whole participant pool, it is evident that there is an equal distribution of 15 female participants and 15 male individuals. The statistics presented in Figures 1, 2, and 3 depict the results of a survey conducted to assess the proficiency of travelers in acting as tourist guides.

Figure 1. Generation X Participants' Views on the Basic Professional Skills of the Tourist Guide

Source: Created by the author

Figure 2. Generation Y Participants' Views on the Basic Professional Skills of Tourist Guides

Source: Created by the author

Figure 3. Generation Z Participants' Views on the Basic Professional Skills of Tourist Guides

Source: Created by the author

Figures 1, 2, and 3 depict the responses pertaining to the inquiry regarding the possession of fundamental professional competencies by the tourist guide. The provided information demonstrates the responses provided in relation to the posed inquiry. When examining the responses provided by persons belonging to Generation X within this particular setting, it becomes evident that various factors, including proficient communication, expert service provision, and a comprehensive understanding of the local culture, are apparent. Currently, it is seen that Generation X correlates the professional competencies of the guide with these variables. Conversely, while considering the professional competencies of a guide for those in the Y generation, elements such as experience, degree of expertise, compelling storytelling, and precise and coherent communication are emphasized. It has been observed that individuals belonging to Generation Y place a greater emphasis on the acquisition of knowledge and the manner in which it is articulated. In contrast, individuals belonging to Generation Z tend to link the leadership position and interpretive skills with the professional competencies of the guide. Within this particular setting, it may be posited that tourists belonging to each of the three generations exhibit distinct areas of focus.

X1: "The tourist guide provided us with a proficient and compelling narrative throughout the duration of the tour." Based on his narrative, we perceived him to possess a high level of professionalism. Therefore, I would want to assert that the guide rendered a service of a professional nature. Furthermore, the guide resided along the itinerary of the tour, so facilitating a comprehensive elucidation of the cultural aspects pertaining to the region.

Y5: "The tour was highly enjoyable." The tourist guide shown a high level of expertise and proficiency in their field. We were content with his storytelling. The guide exhibited a high level of expertise. We were quite struck by his narrative. The event was highly noteworthy. No inquiries were necessary as his elucidations were comprehensive, lucid, and informative. The experience was fulfilling.

The value of Z is 7. The guide assumed the role of a leader. I thoroughly enjoyed it. I have a preference for guided excursions due to my lack of familiarity with the surroundings. The individual demonstrated a high level of proficiency in interpreting and effectively conveying explanations.

Figure 4. Generation X Participants' Views on the Evaluation of the Tourist Guide's Communication Skills
 Source: Created by the author

Figure 5. Generation Y Participants' Views on the Evaluation of Tourist Guide's Communication Skills
 Source: Created by the author

Figure 6. Generation X Participants' Views on the Evaluation of the Tourist Guide's Communication Skills
 Source: Created by the author

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the responses to the question: Can you evaluate the tourist guide in terms of communication skills? The responses to the question are shown. Generation X emphasizes the communication skills of the guide with fun and sympathetic approach features. Generation Y, on the other hand, expresses more factors in communication skills than Generation X and Generation Z. One of them is the use of effective language, harmony with group members and sincere sincere behavior. Individuals in Generation Z emphasize the importance of a strong sense of humor regarding the guide's communication skills.

X:3 "The tourist guide entertained us a lot. He sang local folk songs. He showed very sympathetic attitudes. We were very pleased with his attitudes and behaviors. He constantly chatted with us and explained us".

Y6: "He communicated with us very well. He communicated with each of us one by one. He showed sincere attitudes. He was acting sincerely. His Turkish was beautiful and effective. He used it effectively.

Z4: "We had a lot of fun with the guide. His sense of humor appealed to our age group. His jokes cheered us up. He established a good communication with us".

Figure 7. Views of Generation X on the Evaluation of the Tourist Guide's Relations with Guests

Source: Created by the author

Figure 8. Views of Generation Y on the Evaluation of the Tourist Guide's Relationship with Guests

Source: Created by the author

Figure 9. Views on Generation Z's Evaluation of Tourist Guide's Relations with Guests

Source: Created by the author

Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the responses to the question: Can you evaluate the tour guide's relationship with the guests? The answers given to the question are seen. When the responses are analyzed, it is seen that respectful and fun attitudes are more important for individuals in Generation X. While individuals in the Y generation attach importance to hospitality and sincerity, individuals in the Z generation stated that the tourist guide was sincere and friendly.

X2: "The guide was very respectful. Although there were people in the group who caused problems, he never compromised his respect. He had a polite and calm approach. He also made us laugh a lot. He was a fun young inexperienced but smart boy".

Y4: "The guide was hospitable from the first moment he met us. He had very sincere behavior. We never felt like we were in a foreign place and what he told us stayed in our minds".

Z8: "We felt like we were on a tour with a friend. Although he was not close to us in age, he chatted with us like a friend and made explanations. He had a sincere structure. This gave us a lot of confidence".

Figure 10. Opinions on the Evaluation of the Service Provided by the Tourist Guide

Source: Created by the author

Are you content with the service rendered by the tourist guide, as depicted in Figure 10? The responses provided in relation to the query have been presented. Although all participants from Generation X expressed satisfaction with the service, 8 participants from Generation Y reported being satisfied, while 2 persons indicated dissatisfaction. Within the cohort of Generation Z participants, a total of 7 individuals expressed their contentment, whilst 3 individuals conveyed their dissatisfaction. The reasons for participants who responded negatively to the inquiry on their satisfaction with the offered service are elucidated in Figure 11. Respondents belonging to the Y generation who expressed dissatisfaction with the service provided cited several reasons for their negative response. These individuals reported that the guide's brisk walking pace, subdued vocal delivery, and the tightly structured program were factors

contributing to their overall dissatisfaction. The participants belonging to Generation Z expressed their dissatisfaction with the guide, citing rudeness, inadequate provision of information, failure to take charge of the trip, and inefficiency in time management.

5. Discussions and Conclusion

The function of a tourist guide is of significant importance, necessitating the possession of multiple skills. According to Bowie and Chang (2005), as the range of traits that individuals should possess expands, there is a corresponding increase in the diversification of their fundamental professional skills. The importance of certain fundamental professional qualities for guides, such as effective expression, noteworthy expression, mastery of regional culture, professional service, acceptable level of education, and professional experience, is recognized among

Generations X, Y, and Z. The effective organization of tours, comprehensive understanding of the local culture, proper selection of attire for the tour, informative storytelling, thorough knowledge of the tour route, and extensive professional background are factors that contribute to the existing body of research and deviate from the conclusions drawn in previous studies (Chang, 2012; Khornjamnong, 2017). During guided tours, there is continuous communication between tour guides and guests during the duration of the tour (Pond, 1993). In this particular context, the primary aspect that emerges as crucial in the delivery of a high-quality service by the guide, and is deemed essential for assessing tourists, pertains to possessing effective communication skills. This form of intensive communication necessitates individuals to undertake a range of tasks (Carlzon, 1987). The present study examines the evaluation of the guide's communication,

focusing on the distinct aspects emphasized by individuals from different generations. Currently, the findings of this research make a valuable contribution to the existing body of literature. According to the frequency of recurrence, the guide's communication abilities that are deemed crucial for Generation X include a sympathetic approach, a good attitude, and an element of fun. The results align with the existing body of research (Huang, Hsu, & Chan, 2010). The millennial generation demonstrates proficiency in language usage, the tendency to engage in distracting discourse, and the ability to maintain harmonious relationships within a group. Millennials express dissatisfaction with the guide's deficient communication abilities through the manifestation of speech that is bothersome in nature. Once again, this outcome is regarded as a novel manifestation that has the potential to make a valuable contribution to the existing body of literature. Furthermore, the literature provides additional support for the positive outcomes resulting from the proficient utilization of language, as evidenced by studies conducted by Moutinho et al. (2015). In contrast to the preceding generations, Generation Z members exhibit a heightened emphasis on comedy and explanatory narrative as key components of their communication abilities. The literature provides support for the conclusions pertaining to Generation Z (Lin et al., 2016). When comparing the three generations, it becomes evident that the participants place significance on distinct factors during the process of communication. The responses provided pertaining to communication skills exhibit similarities with the conclusions drawn from many scholarly investigations (Zhang & Chow, 2004; Min, 2015; Nguyen, 2015; Chan, Hsu & Baum, 2015). Nonetheless, the absence of a comprehensive investigation on the potential disparities across generations, as indicated by the existing body of literature, serves as the distinctive aspect of this study and contributes to its theoretical significance.

Upon analyzing the outcomes of the interaction between the tourist guide and the guests, it becomes evident that the guide distinguishes himself through his amicable and enjoyable demeanor with persons belonging to Generation X. Participants from Generation Y remark that the guide exhibits authenticity and a welcoming demeanor. The guide's genuine and amicable nature is particularly prominent among persons belonging to Generation Z. The research findings provide support for the studies documented in the existing literature (Huang, Hsu & Chan, 2010; Min, 2015). The scholarly research in this domain presents varying perspectives on the manner in which guides interact with guests, contrasting with the aforementioned negative attributes such as indifference, distrust, lack of professionalism, and

impoliteness. It is evident that the entirety of the participants belonging to Generation X express contentment with the service rendered by the guide. However, it can be inferred that certain participants from Generations Y and Z exhibit dissatisfaction with the aforementioned service. The factors contributing to discontent among persons belonging to Generation Y encompass brisk walking, congested schedules, and low vocal intonation. Conversely, participants from Generation Z express unhappiness arising from circumstances such as erroneous seat allocation and impulsive conduct. Upon analyzing the responses of the participants regarding their satisfaction with the service rendered by the tourist guide, it becomes evident that there are notable variations in the evaluation of the service across different generations. The present discovery demonstrates that the investigation yields distinct outcomes contingent upon the research's objective. Within the present environment, it is evident that there exists a disparity in the impression of service quality among different generations when it comes to tourist guides. The findings of this study provide a theoretical contribution to the existing body of knowledge. As an additional area of inquiry, it is recommended to explore the potential intergenerational variations in the impact of service quality provided by guides on overall satisfaction. The study is anticipated to provide a beneficial impact on educational institutions that offer guided education, particularly in relation to the educational development of pupils. It is recommended that students engage in their professional practice by taking into account the generational disparities among tourists. Concurrently, experienced guides in this field should align their service delivery with intergenerational distinctions. The topic of interest pertains to the variations in package trips offered by travel businesses throughout different generations.

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